

Involving the Defense Industry in the Innovative Development process of the Civil Industry

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Аннотация. Одна из первоочередных задач любого государства – обеспечение своего оборонного потенциала и национальной безопасности. За последнее десятилетие российское правительство вложило значительные физические и человеческие ресурсы в укрепление вооруженных сил. В результате этой работы ОПК стал одним из центров передовых технологий, знаний и высококвалифицированных кадров. Как показывает мировой опыт, эти ресурсы могут быть эффективно использованы в процессе диверсификации оборонного производства в целях повышения технологической эффективности и конкурентоспособности гражданской промышленности. Таким образом, целью исследования является анализ и систематизация международного опыта процесса диверсификации ОПК. Для достижения этой цели мы проанализировали экономические исследования, посвященные этой теме, и статистические данные. Результаты исследования включают конкретные рекомендации, помогающие создать эффективную систему управления и контроля процесса диверсификации. Такая система должна базироваться на интеграции военного и гражданского секторов, взаимосвязи науки, образования и бизнеса и включать методы оценки ее эффективности. Процессы диверсификации и интеграции ускоряют трансфер технологий, активизируют инновационную деятельность предприятий, будут способствовать переходу на 6-й технологический уклад, что имеет особое значение для России в нынешних ограниченных условиях.

Abstract. One of the primary tasks of any state is to maintain its defense potential and its national security. The Russian government has invested significant physical and human resources in the last decade to strengthen the armed forces. As a result of this work the defense industry complex has become one of the hubs of advanced technologies, knowledge and highly skilled personnel. As proved by the international experience, these resources can be used efficiently in the process of diversification of defense production for the purpose of enhancement of technological efficiency and competitiveness of the civilian industry. Thus, the aim of the study is to analyze and systematize the international experience in the defense industry diversification process. In order to achieve this goal, we have analyzed economic studies devoted to this topic and statistical data. The results of a study include specific recommendations helping to set up efficient management and control system of the diversification process. Such system should be based on the integration of the military and civilian sectors, interconnection of science, education and business and involve the methods of assessment of its effectiveness. The processes of diversification and integration will accelerate the transfer of technologies, intensify the innovative activity of enterprises, contribute to the transition to the 6th technological mode, which is of particular importance for Russia in the current restrictive conditions.

Ключевые слова: *инновационность, конкурентоспособность, инновационное развитие, человеческий капитал.*

Keywords: *defense industry complex, diversification, conversion, high technologies, civilian industry, technology transfer, foreign experience.*

Introduction

The defense industry complex (DIC) of Russia has long been the core of innovation activities since defense enterprises are three times more active in this process than civil ones [1]. Moreover, the military sector may be considered as the driver of research and technological development because it is in possession of highly qualified human resources, financial and other resource support from the state.

At the end of the geopolitical conflict, the release of capacity and resources of defense enterprises can be rationally used to establish the manufacture of high-tech civilian products [2]. However, it is necessary to assess to what extent labor and capital assets can be used at civilian enterprises, in what way the production technologies can be adapted [3].

Diversification is the most obvious way of transferring military technologies. In addition, the task of diversification was reflected in the state industrial policy prior to the special military operation. The launch of the state armament program in 2009, which covered the period from 2010 to 2020, intensified the Russian scientists' interest in the study of various aspects of diversification of the Russian DIC. A number of scientists devoted their research work to the issues of diversification: E.Yu. Khrustalev [4], A.M. Batkovsky [1,5-6], A.E. Varshavsky [2], O.S. Sukharev [7], V.V. Klochkov [8], V.V. Ivanter [9], S.I. Dovguchits [10], D.A. Zhurenkov [11], A.A. Shirov and I.E. Frolov [12].

Active research of diversify process was started in the USA in the late 1960s [11; 13]. The reduced defense spending forced the dependent companies to look for other markets, to repurpose

their products, to develop new ones and to restructure their facilities. This prompted American researchers towards elaborating a model of parallel development of a new product [14].

The end of the Cold War and disintegration of the Soviet Union exacerbated the need to diversify the defense sector of the NATO members [15]. English scientists assessed the interrelation between diversification and labor productivity [3] and considered the features of diversification and conversion, their consequences and differences [13; 16].

With the end of the Cold War diversification issues affected also the developing countries. For example, research made in India illustrated how difficult it was for a developing country to be fully self-sufficient in production of high-tech items for its defense in the absence of partnership between the defense and high-tech civilian sectors [17].

The number of scholarly studies devoted to diversification is increasing, but no coherent system of scientific knowledge has been formed yet, which in practice leads to the use of the “trial and error” method [5; 18]. The conceptual apparatus and the stages of target planning of diversification activities have not been defined.

The paper is structured as follows. The methodology section describes the methods used in the study which helped to conduct a comparison of military expenditures and identify the main features and peculiarities of the DIC that have to deal with in the process of diversification. The results section provides an analysis of the global experience of successful and not successful diversification and

conversion process, identifies scenarios of this process, defines the list of problems faced by defense and civilian enterprises. The discussion section is dedicated to the development of the system of consistent steps to ensure the success of the diversification process. The conclusion presents the key results of the study.

Materials and Methods

Following the purpose of the research, which is to conduct the analysis and systematization of the world experience of the DIC diversification, the following research methods were chosen: collection, analysis and comparison of statistical data on military expenditures, analysis of domestic and foreign literature on the object of the research - the DIC diversification. The study solves the following research tasks: identifying systemic problems of the diversification process based on foreign experience; analyzing approaches to solving these problems; evaluating the applicability of foreign experience in Russia; developing the system of measures to improve the effectiveness of the diversification process. The research period covers about 20 years starting from 1990s. It should be noted that the available information used in the study is limited due to the secrecy of the DIC.

Russia spends near 6% of the GDP on defense. This is a quite large figure compared with the military spending in the developed countries, such as the United States and France (see Figure 1). This figure is larger only in the Middle East countries, such as Oman, Saudi Arabia and Kuwait, ranging from 7-14% in different periods.

Fig. 1. Evolution of military spending in selected countries, % of GDP
Source: SIPRI: <https://www.sipri.org/databases/milex>

Russia in monetary terms ranked first in Europe and fourth in the world in military spending by the end of 2020, after the USA, the PRC and India.

The present study is methodologically based on the analysis of publications of foreign and Russian authors addressing the socio-economic aspects and problems of diversification of the military-industrial complex, described in the introduction.

This analysis showed the defense industry complex has a number of features. First, DIC is characterized by quasi-market relations, when the only customer dictates. Second, the governmental regulation of prices in this sector influences the internal production chain pricing when it is profitable to increase the labor intensity of orders. It is not uncommon when a contract binding for defense companies is knowingly

unprofitable but a company has no right to withdraw from the contract. Obviously, in such cases revenues and profitability decline and the enterprise is looking for the ways to make profit or tries to cut the costs. This may involve getting rid of non-core assets that are often socially important, closing unprofitable jobs, transferring employees to a shortened work week, unpaid leaves, reducing resource costs and overcoming institutional barriers. Third, the production units may have a complex system of cooperation with a great number of components and complex technological processes [10]. It should also be remembered that military products have a long manufacturing cycle of 10-15 years and are often unique, which requires considerable advance payments as to labor remuneration and procurement and leads to increased costs and reduced profitability of contracts [19].

These features of DIC have shaped several industry problems that can be solved through diversification. The first problem is "cost-plus" pricing which precludes the reasons to reduce costs. The second problem is the lack of investors and the third problem is withdrawal of highly skilled personnel and ageing of the workforce.

It is worth noting that DIC not only involves high public budget expenditure; this sector is characterized by concentration of resources and highly qualified personnel, as well as advanced development of science, high technologies, production; availability of numerous suppliers in this area. With the reduction of the SDP, diversification appears to be a realistic way for defense companies to enter the market, and for civilian sectors – a source of high technologies and knowledge.

Results

The experience of American military corporations has demonstrated that a long-term focus on military needs and a minor share of civilian products leads to loss of competitiveness in the market and difficulties in entering the market; therefore, all US defense companies are interested in diversification [20]. It is rational to make decisions in respect of particular defense companies and to outsource some part of production to civilian companies [21].

China's policy of diversification pursued in the 1980s allowed to increase the civilian products to account for 80% in the gross output of defense enterprises by the early 2000s. For instance, China's DIC became a basis for the civil aviation and automotive industry [11]. Currently, the diversification policy of the Chinese DIC follows the European scenario, through integration with high-tech civilian companies. This type of diversification makes it possible to use civilian technologies in the DIC sphere. This is particularly relevant for the USA and Europe, since the development of civilian sector technologies takes place presently at a very fast pace, outstripping the military sector [22].

Based on the Israeli experience, it may be stated that efficient conversion requires a comprehensive industrial policy which focuses not only on

investment in research and technological development, but also on development of human capital and commercialization in the long term [23, p.137–166]. The need for state support of talents and technologies both at defense and civilian enterprises as well as for development of entrepreneurial activity in this sphere is confirmed by the experience of India. Moreover, it shows that heavy state regulation hinders creativity and nullifies restructuring efforts; therefore, efficient conversion requires institutional change [17, p.195–216].

In the scientific literature diffusion of technologies is viewed in two aspects: as a tool for innovation and technological development of civilian industries and as a joint technological platform of the military and civilian sectors of the national economy [24]. The transfer of military technologies to the civilian sector, according to the world practice, may follow several scenarios. The first, most common scenario is production of civilian products on the basis of a military enterprise. The second option is DIC enterprise's sale of technologies that do not carry the risk of disclosure of military secrets or threat of misuse; the third scenario is integration of military and civilian enterprises on the basis of the defense potential. The fourth scenario assumes that the civilian sector commissions research and technological development to a military enterprise, while the fifth option assumes that the government involves defense enterprises in state-run programs such as road construction [24].

Russia's conversion experience has shown that the national DIC enterprises can be divided into three types:

- 1) enterprises that are not in the position to produce civilian goods (e.g. involved in production of nuclear weapons and special ammunition)
- 2) enterprises that need active state support for diversification, because the standalone position of the complex in the soviet epoch, the secrecy of technologies, significant investments have a negative impact on transfer of technologies and profitability [25-26].
- 3) enterprises that are able to independently shift to the "civilian path", for instance, aircraft building and shipbuilding corporations, enterprises producing medical equipment. Usually, such enterprises already have a significant share of civil products in the gross output [27].

The task of finding an optimal ratio for military and civilian products requires well-thought-of fine-tuning of the entire governmental industrial policy in order to mitigate the problems inevitably faced by defense enterprises in their efforts to shift to new markets and areas of activity [28]. The product structure change without clean-cut schemes can lead to reduction in output, as was the case in Russia in the 1990s [20].

The list of problems faced by defense enterprises in production of civilian items has been compiled repeatedly by different authors and may be as follows:

1. The barriers to civilian market entry, such as patenting, licensing and certification, which may require significant capital investment to overcome the above. The manufacture of civilian products is impossible without technical documentation which is a rather costly item not affordable to any enterprise [21].

2. Positioning and promotion in the civilian market. It's about brand, reputation and image. Outlining the target audience is important for promotion in the market.

3. High-tech products require after-sales service, continuous improvements and upgrade. Customers, reputation and hence profits get lost because of the poor quality of the provided service.

4. The inability to react quickly to changes in the market due to the specific pricing of military products and the high level of competition with manufacturers of similar products, both local and foreign. The state can regulate the prices for civilian products manufactured by defense enterprises.

5. The lack of resources – financial, human, information – and blurred priorities in distribution of these resources have an extremely negative impact on product competitiveness and exacerbate the above-mentioned problems. In order to produce competitive products, the enterprise should have necessary capacities ready to manufacture high-tech products, as well as due engineering and managerial staff, suppliers and resources. It is not enough to have high technologies; it is necessary to set up the production as proper, in line with them.

To function efficiently, a diversified defense enterprise will have to go through the institutional transformation.

Introduction of products to the market and maintaining a due level of competitiveness over a long term is not possible without competent marketing, design and administrative expertise [28].

Based on the experience of other countries it can be concluded that before starting a diversification process, it is advisable to assess what type of enterprise a company belongs to and to what extent it is prepared for diversification. The organization of restructuring process for each enterprise in the defense industry complex requires individual approach focused on establishment of new areas of commercial use of military technologies. The danger here lies in the possibility of falling into the institutional trap of inefficient management [29]. One of the main problems arising in diversification of production is creation of efficient mechanism for management and control of diversification and transfer of high technologies from DIC to the civilian sphere. Competent management of innovative projects allows accelerating their development and bringing them to the mass production stage.

The article repeatedly stresses that the modern DIC structure in the world practice increasingly focuses on a joint business model for enterprises, dual-use products, and integration of military technologies in civilian life [30]. The integration of mili-

tary and civilian enterprises within the framework of technological cooperation can take place on the basis of technology parks or industrial clusters.

Outsourcing of technology or production of certain parts and components to civilian enterprises does not require DIC enterprises to develop civilian products in a protracted and costly way or sell them in the market. A company-transferee of military technologies should have an advantage of knowing the market and the practice of entering the market, which will help to overcome some problems. At the same time, military companies can help civilian enterprises in promotion of products: normally defense companies have access to international markets.

However, technology-adopting contractors, who are first-tier suppliers, as well as their subcontractors, who are second-tier suppliers, must be prepared to significantly restructure their business operations in order to be competitive in the market. With no changes in the approach to product development, manufacture, quality improvement and organization of due distribution channels, the transition from culture based on state orders to a buyer-driven culture will not take place, and the reconstruction of sales and marketing channels will not yield the desired results.

The joint work of defense companies with civilian enterprises in the sphere of production of components will contribute to the formation of a competitive national base of technical components, which is a key to stable and smooth operation of any enterprise, especially in the complicated political and socio-economic conditions [31]. The American experience of diversification shows that it is necessary to involve civilian companies, such as Google, as well as universities and start-up companies [32].

Many authors insist on the need to develop a system of criteria and indicators to assess the efficiency of diversification [18]. Moreover, such a system, which supposes a conceptual framework, risk analysis methods and proper systems for monitoring the company standing and the market situation, etc., will have to be developed by every enterprise taking into account its own specifics.

The need to integrate science and education into the process of diversification and integration should not be overlooked. The use of the triple helix model – interaction of science, education and business – will accelerate the process of technology transfer from DIC to the civilian sector and contribute to the transition of the national economy to the new technological paradigm [33].

Discussion

Diversification of defense industry is a complex, long-term process depending on many factors and elements. The defense market, having a number of unique characteristics, does not work well at commercial markets. Therefore, the first step towards diversification should involve assessment of feasibility and practicability of civilian production at a particular defense enterprise. For this purpose, in-

ternal audit is carried out: technologies, enterprise development strategy, diversification resources are evaluated. Experts in venture capital funding and market research, representing the agencies dealing in survey of high-tech product markets, are involved in this audit. As a result of this analysis, military enterprises not fit for diversification remain unaffected, while integrated structures develop a due action plan for diversification.

Defense assets can be much specific, and significant barriers may have to be overcome to ensure efficient diversification. The companies going through this process need to be committed, persistent and ready for transformation. Management of a large defense firm requires development of special management logic, distinctive from other businesses.

Efficient diversification requires careful restructuring of business operations and willingness to take risks in order to achieve the performance needed to enter- and compete in target markets. Creating a competitive product portfolio is the next step of the diversification process. This portfolio should meet the market needs and take into account the company's resource. To succeed in this process, not only state-of-the-art equipment is required, but also highly skilled and motivated employees, due company-wide quality control systems, plus competent strategic planning making it possible to match the company's core competencies with the new market opportunities and to compete effectively in the rapidly changing commercial market environment in the long term. The tight integration of research, production, design and marketing will achieve excellence in product quality, pricing and customer service, while establishing due cooperation with suppliers, customers and competitors will help to handle the positioning issues in commercial markets.

Changing the corporate culture towards active management encourages employees' involvement in this process and orientation at the needs of the target audience, since there is a huge difference in selling products to a broad range of consumers or firms and selling to a sole political customer in the defense market. The convergence of military and civilian business cultures is a rather complex process; therefore, creating an efficient management system for diversification purposes is one of the most important challenges [34]. To meet this challenge, the researchers suggest, for instance, that a coordination center should be established to set the development ways for DIC enterprises [25].

Allowing private capital in the defense complex will as well encourage top managers towards proactive position, since the investor, represented by the state, controls only the issues of fulfilment of state orders and not the issues of return on invested capital.

The alternative view on diversification insists that profit can be increased by reducing competition rather than by increasing efficiency. Large, diversi-

fied firms are in the position to engage in anti-competitive practices like cross-subsidization, predatory pricing, reciprocity in buying and selling and raising barriers to entry [31]. The demerits may include the return of demand for defense products, high profits from sale of military equipment, especially in case of opportunity to enter new markets, difficult and lengthy process of adjustment to commercial markets, investor wariness about the diversification process.

Conclusion

The study shows that the development strategy of Russian high-tech civilian industries has to be based on DIC resources especially in the context of sanctions. In the current complex political and socio-economic conditions DIC can become a source of technologies for the civil sector and a basis for scientific and technological development of the civilian industries. The defense sector diversification will allow the enterprises to raise profits, enhance investment attractiveness, expand the product portfolio and increase its competitiveness.

However, it should be more than a technology transfer and search for markets. Full-fledged integration of the military and civilian sectors with the involvement of private capital is required. DIC may act as a technology consumer by commissioning its development to a high-tech small or medium-size enterprise. Much of the 20th century technological breakthrough achievements were a product of civilian research and technological development; therefore, civilian science research should not be underestimated.

This process cannot be achieved and successful without comprehensive industrial policy aimed not only at investment in R&D, but also at developing human capital and restoring the relationship between science, education and industry.

Diversification cannot be implemented without state support. The function of the state should not be limited to the investor's role: it should become the organizer and regulator of this process. The enterprises will need information support and up-to-date flexible legislative and regulatory framework, especially in the field of intellectual property protection and information security, as well as assistance in fine-tuning of the infrastructure.

Diversification of DIC enterprises and joint production of military- and civilian-usage products is a relevant scientific problem. A joint technological platform of military and civilian sectors makes it possible to increase the competitiveness and variety of the produced products, increase innovation activity and accelerate the shift to the new technological mode.

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